

Breaking Down Data Silos: Launch of HealthData4EU Cluster Promises Groundbreaking Healthcare Innovations

The future of healthcare just got a whole lot brighter with the launch of a dynamic cluster of sister projects funded under the prestigious **HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-02 call**. This synergistic endeavor brings together leading-edge initiatives, each committed to **leveraging technology to advance patient care and dismantle data silos**.

At the heart of this initiative is a collective mission: **to harness cutting-edge technologies and drive impactful change in healthcare delivery**. With a focus on enhancing accessibility and efficiency in patient care, these projects are poised to revolutionize the healthcare landscape across the European Union

Introducing the Projects:

- **SYNTHEMA:** Breaking barriers in rare hematological diseases, SYNTHEMA aims to establish a cross-border health data hub. By pioneering AI-based techniques for clinical data anonymization and synthetic data generation, SYNTHEMA seeks to address data scarcity and fragmentation, paving the way for GDPR-compliant research in this critical area. Visit our [website](#) for more info.
- **PHASE IV AI:** Advancing AI in healthcare, PHASE IV AI pioneers synthetic data generation to overcome barriers in data accessibility and privacy. By developing state-of-the-art synthesis methods and privacy-compliant protocols, PHASE IV AI accelerates the adoption of AI-powered tools for preventive healthcare and clinical decision-making. Visit our [website](#) for more info.
- **SECURED:** Spearheading a cross-border health data collaboration ecosystem, SECURED offers a secure collaboration hub for decentralized processing of health data. Through Privacy Preserving Computation techniques such as secure multiparty computation (SMPC) or Homomorphic

Encryption (HE) and synthetic data generation, SECURED facilitates innovation in health data analytics and fosters collaboration among stakeholders. Visit our [website](#) for more info.

- **FLUTE:** Revolutionizing healthcare data utilization, FLUTE enhances predictions of aggressive prostate cancer through privacy-preserving AI support to physicians. By minimizing unnecessary biopsies, FLUTE improves patient outcomes and reduces healthcare costs. Visit our [website](#) for more info.
- **PHEMS:** Leading the change in pediatric healthcare innovation, PHEMS establishes a decentralized health data ecosystem. By leveraging federated analytics and machine learning, PHEMS transforms pediatric care for children's hospitals. Visit our [website](#) for more info.
- **AI Sym4Med:** Aims to develop a platform that will provide healthcare data engineers, practitioners, and researchers access to a trustworthy dataset system augmented with controlled data synthesis for experimentation and modeling purposes. This platform will address data privacy and security by combining new anonymization techniques, attribute-based privacy measures, and trustworthy tracking systems. Visit our [website](#) for more info.

About Horizon-HLTH-2022-IND-13-02:

The Horizon-HLTH-2022-IND-13-02 call is a flagship initiative aimed at funding innovative projects that **leverage technology to enhance healthcare services and address critical healthcare challenges**. Through strategic funding and collaboration, the program aims to drive impactful change in healthcare delivery and improve patient outcomes.

These projects align with the objectives outlined in HORIZON-HLTH-2022-IND-13-02, scaling up multi-party computation, data anonymization techniques, and synthetic data generation to address critical healthcare challenges. By fostering secure, interoperable, and transparent cross-border health data hubs, these initiatives facilitate the development and adoption of innovative data-driven solutions. Developers now have access to advanced secure data processing tools, enabling the testing and development of robust digital health products and services. Furthermore, the utilization of synthetic data allows for large-scale experimentation without compromising individual privacy, while sophisticated anonymization techniques ensure GDPR compliance and protect sensitive information.

The launch of this groundbreaking cluster marks a significant milestone in healthcare innovation. Together, these projects are poised to drive transformative change, delivering impactful solutions and advancing patient care worldwide.

For more information on individual projects and collaborative opportunities, please **visit project websites.**

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